

Cleavage of Se-Se bond by Sm/cat.CoCl₂ system : a facile and novel method for the preparation of selenoesters

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The Sm/cat.CoCl₂ system promoted diselenides to react with anhydrides or acyl chlorides to afford selenoesters in good yields under mild and neutral conditions.

Samarium diiodide is a powerful one electron transfer reductant¹. It has widely been applied in organic synthesis^{2,3}. Though SmI₂ is a useful reagent, storage is difficult because it is very sensitive to air oxidation. On the other hand, metallic samarium is stable in air and has strong reducing power (Sm³⁺/Sm = -2.41 V) similar to that of magnesium (Mg²⁺/Mg = -2.37 V). These properties promoted us to use the more convenient and cheaper metallic samarium directly as a reducing agent instead of SmI₂. Selenoesters are useful intermediates in the synthesis of natural compounds⁴, but, relatively few synthesis of selenoesters have been described. A useful approach to the synthesis of selenoesters is the reaction of acyl halide with selenol^{4,5}. Another approach is based on the

alkylation of selenolate ion⁶. These methods have been applied successfully to the synthesis of selenoesters. In our previous work we had found successfully a facile preparation of selenoesters by cleavage of Se-Se bond with SmI₂.

Results and discussion

Here, we wish to report the Sm/cat.CoCl₂ system promoted diselenides to react with anhydrides or acyl chlorides to afford selenoesters in good yields in THF at RT (Scheme 1). The results are listed in Table 1. Some control experiments revealed that Se-Se bond could not be cleaved by Sm or CoCl₂ alone. Therefore, according to the relative report⁸ we suggested the following possible

Table 1. Reaction with anhydrides and acyl chlorides

Entry	Ar	R ₁ or R ₂	Product	Yield (%)
For anhydrides :				
1	Ph	CH ₃	PhSeC(O)CH ₃	70
2	Ph	CH ₃ CH ₂	PhSeC(O)CH ₂ CH ₃	77
3	Ph	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂	PhSeC(O)CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	80
4	Ph	Ph	PhSeC(O)Ph	62
5	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SeC(O)CH ₃	75
6	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃ CH ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SeC(O)CH ₂ CH ₃	79
7	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃ CH ₂ CH ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SeC(O)CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	77
For acyl chlorides :				
1	Ph	CH ₃	PhSeC(O)CH ₃	79
2	Ph	CH ₃ CH ₂	PhSeC(O)CH ₂ CH ₃	78
3	Ph	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₃ CH ₂	PhSeC(O)(CH ₂) ₄ CH ₃	69
4	Ph	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₉ CH ₂	PhSeC(O)(CH ₂) ₁₀ CH ₃	63
5	Ph	Ph	PhSeC(O)Ph	65
6	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SeC(O)CH ₃	77
7	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃ CH ₂	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ SeC(O)CH ₂ CH ₃	80

*Isolated yields.

Scheme 1

mechanism : (a) one electron reduction of cobalt(II) to cobalt(I) by samarium metal, (b) oxidative carbonylation of cobalt(I) by anhydrides or acyl chlorides to RC(O)Co^{III} and (c) reaction of RC(O)Co^{III} with diselenides liberating Co^{II} and product selenoester. In other words, the strategy invokes a tandem process involving Co^{II}, Co^I and Co^{III} intermediates and is also catalytic with respect to cobalt (Scheme 2). However, the exact mechanism is not fully clarified and a more detailed study is in progress in our laboratory. In conclusion, we have demonstrated Sm/cat.CoCl₂ system can be used for the preparation of selenoesters via the cleavage of the Se-Se bond. The experimental simplicity, mild reaction condition and good yield provides a new way for using metallic samarium in organic synthesis.

Scheme 2

Experimental

Metallic samarium and other chemicals were purchased from commercial sources and used without purification. Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was distilled from sodium/benzophenone immediately prior to use. All reactions were carried on under a dry nitrogen atmosphere.

Melting points were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 683 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Bruker AC-400 instrument. All NMR samples were measured in CCl₄ using TMS as internal standard.

Metallic samarium powder (1.0 mmol), cobalt(II) chloride (0.2 mmol) and diaryl diselenide (0.5 mmol) were placed in a three-necked reaction flask and THF (10 ml) was added in one portion. Anhydride or acyl chloride (1.2 mmol) was then added to the mixture and stirred at RT for 5 h. A diluted solution of HCl was added to quench the reaction and the mixture was extracted with diethyl ether (20 ml × 2). The organic layer was washed with water (20 ml × 2) and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was removed *in vacuo*. The residue was then purified by preparative TLC on silica gel (cyclohexane-ethyl acetate as eluent) to give pure product : PhSeC(O)CH₃⁴; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3095, 3090, 2950, 2880, 2860, 1740, 1600, 1580, 1480, 1440, 1350, 1100, 1070, 1010, 1000, 935, 730, 670 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 2.39 (3H, s), 7.40 (5H, m); PhSeC(O)CH₂CH₃⁹; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3100, 3080, 2950, 2870, 1740, 1590, 1570, 1470, 1440, 1350, 1100, 1070, 1000, 940, 690, 660 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 1.16 (3H, t), 2.51 (2H, q), 7.40 (5H, m); PhSeC(O)CH₂CH₂CH₃¹⁰; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3090, 3080, 2960, 2870, 1740, 1600, 1570, 1475, 1440, 1360, 1100, 1070, 1010, 940, 690, 660 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 1.10 (3H, t), 1.60 (2H, m), 2.54 (2H, t), 7.40 (5H, m); PhSeC(O)Ph⁴; m.p. 40–41° (lit. 42°); IR (ν_{max}) 3090, 3080, 1745, 1600, 1590, 1480, 1450, 1250, 1200, 1175, 1110, 1020, 1000, 870, 840, 760, 740, 680, 660, 620 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 7.23–7.57 (8H, m), 7.77–7.93 (2H, m); *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SeC(O)CH₃¹¹; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3080, 3020, 2980, 2950, 1745, 1600, 1570, 1540, 1480, 1450, 1350, 1280, 1200, 1100, 1060, 1020, 935, 730, 660 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 2.34 (3H, s), 2.41 (3H, s), 7.32 (4H, m); *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SeC(O)CH₂CH₃⁹; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3095, 3080, 2980, 2950, 1745, 1650, 1580, 1550, 1480, 1450, 1360, 1270, 1200, 1100, 1060, 1020, 940, 730, 660 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 1.25 (3H, t), 2.34 (3H, s), 2.60 (2H, q), 7.32 (4H, m); *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SeC(O)CH₂CH₂CH₃⁹; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3090, 3080, 2980, 2950, 1745, 1660, 1600, 1560, 1480, 1460, 1370, 1260, 1200, 1100, 1060, 1020, 940, 740, 670 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 1.24 (3H, t), 1.60 (2H, m), 2.35 (3H, s), 2.61 (2H, t), 7.32 (4H, m); PhSeC(O)CH₂(CH₂)₉CH₃¹²; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3100, 3085, 2980–2920, 2870, 1745, 1590, 1480, 1460, 1120, 1020, 1000, 740, 690 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (δ_H) 0.87 (3H, t), 1.10–1.40 (6H, m), 2.60 (2H, t), 7.33 (5H, m); PhSeC(O)CH₂(CH₂)₉CH₃¹³; oil; IR (ν_{max}) 3100, 3085, 2980–2920,

2870, 1745, 1600, 1480, 1440, 1120, 1020, 1000, 730, 680 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (δ_{H}) 0.84 (3H, t), 1.10–1.47 (18H, m), 2.60 (2H, t), 7.33 (5H, m).

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